

Editorial

Poo-blication: Flowers, Turds and Mathematics Education Research

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The Journal

ABSTRACT: I conclude my tenure as Editor-in-Chief with a psychoanalysis of the state of mathematics education research and academic publishing. The text particularly criticizes the current “epistemological moment” in 2025, the ways that our field’s discourse has contributed to it, and the ways in which ideology polices the work of the academic in their unconscious. In my analysis, I bolster previous claims of the sexual origins of education. I claim—by simply observing the current context—that revolution in educational research is only possible with the choice of a particular mindset; in this text, I describe my choice for this path forward as well as the desire that makes me choose it. I intend for the reader to “read in between the lines” of this text.

KEYWORDS: *analogy; critique; educational research; edacastration; academic publishing*

“The capitalist world is not shit, and it is not the paradise of the coprophiles whom it indeed represses; it is rather the monstrous shit fetish.”

—Mario Mieli (2018), *Towards a Gay Communism*

Reading the Unreadable

If it is a truism our field is attempting to remedy or cure the infections of educating mathematics, and that we do so through the consumption and production of published research, then it should be rather clear to me what my role has been as Editor-in-Chief of the *Journal* for four years. When I and several others joined forces to found this journal in 2021, in the midst of the COVID-19 pandemic, I—at least for one—was clamoring to be delivered from the anxiety I got from reading mathematics education research. Usually, when I read it, I feel more confused at the end: how do these results relate to my *actual* students? Before my Ph.D., I was a middle school mathematics teacher. The contradictions of that job led me into my doctoral studies, trying to find some “answers.” If I had to guess, I was so indoctrinated into mathematical discourse that I assumed there were answers... somewhere—maybe they were “my own answers” and I just needed to create them. But, in any case, it seemed to be a solvable problem, a completable proof;

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the answers seemed to be *a priori* as a matter of reality. Perhaps it was youthful naïveté. Perhaps it was my masculine-quilted-speech or my ideological belief in the readability of bodies (Moore, 2023). Perhaps some of both. I had a lot to still learn, maybe I still do; the more I have “learned,” the more I have realized that “learning or not learning” is anything but a clear phenomenon. I guess the more I have learned, the more I don’t seem interested in reading most of what is out there in our field’s “usual” genre; the literature that conveys surety, so authoritative in its knowledge, so linear in its conclusions. I have learned throughout life to be skeptical when someone tells you “this is the right way to do this” or “this is the answer.” It’s humorous to realize that these are the same grievances aired by so many students of mathematics.

Somewhere rather early in this process, I was fortunate to come across Lacan’s psychoanalysis, Hegel’s philosophy, Marx’s political economy, and Žižek’s extrapolative syntheses of them. Note the surprise of Lacan’s perspective: “[For Lacan], to ‘cure’ patients was an irrelevant project” (Marini, 1992, p. 3). Well, then, what’s the point? Žižek (1989/2008) gave me my first answer to this question: *there is (also) a desire of the Other*.

Finally, I had something interesting to think about in mathematics education. Rather than looking for cures, it seemed a lot more important to me to discern the reasons for the symptoms I observe in the field, chiefly amongst which resides that symptom of educational research in its usual form. Since our field is roughly called a “human science” or “social science” it seemed obvious to admit that the field’s symptoms are linked to (if not the same as) the *symptoms of the subjects* (teachers, researchers, students) of mathematics education. This is where Lacan has proven to illuminative and liberatory for me. Unfortunately, reading Lacan was quite difficult at first, and had it not been for the isolation afforded me by the pandemic and the selfless help of a few well-known Lacanians in our field, I might not have set my mind to understanding it.

I quickly gained an understanding of why I did not see it more prominently in modern academic discourse: it’s scary. It neuters us, so to say, by coaching us to confront our *jouissance* (roughly: pain/pleasure/excitation) and our fantasies. In doing so, we learn that ideology controls us; we realize that our actions have alienated us from knowing *what is real*. This experience taught me why we continue to seek more cures for symptoms—just for some relief. It taught me that the only possible (real) answers are the *reasons* for our symptoms. And, it taught me that—because we enjoy our symptoms—their reasons are the stones that build the foundation of our being. Hence, I realized that the answers (viz. reasons) I sought were *not* the ones that would yield “helpful directives” for my teaching. Founding this journal was part of my most earnest search for reasons. I feel much less anxiety now than four years ago, and much of it is due to knowing that this journal exists, and that it has garnered an amount of repute and credibility that—honestly—I have been surprised by given the timeframe.

Marini (1992) clarified the unintelligible character of Lacan’s work, saying that the “problem of dissemination of Lacan’s published and unpublished works is so complex that I have devoted part of my first chapter to it” (p. 4). Marini goes on to illustrate Lacan’s own concern about the complications of trying to disseminate his work with the following example:

[S]omeone attended one of Lacan’s unpublished seminars² or found a copy of it; s/he then revises the concepts in his/her own name, in return for a few quotes, isolated from their context and unverifiable by the audience (or the reader). This situation is repeated, from place to place, where everyone’s discourse becomes in turn the Master’s discourse. The

² When this book was published in 1992, most of Lacan’s seminars were unavailable in printed form. This situation has since changed with decades of work by Jacques-Alain Miller editing the Seminar series which continues to see new editions released every handful of years, in addition to the digitization work of Cormac Gallagher and Tony Hughes providing high-quality private-use translations of all of Lacan’s seminars.

annuity [of these practices] is both symbolic and financially concrete, since psychoanalytic teaching, which is generally a private teaching, is very expensive. Lacan used a harsher expression to describe these practices: he talked about the *poubellication* (trashing by publishing) of his work. (Marini, 1992, p. 4)

To me, this speaks to the same concerns I have about the general state of educational research, and it is my position that the field of mathematics education is suffering from this plight quite severely. Educational research is almost univocally signified using this “*à-la-carte* buffet” method: you locate some interesting issue or question, decide under consultation with existing literature what your methodology shall be, pick a theory that seems to “internally align” with the type of research question and data that you have, and then almost mechanically go through the motions of “constructing” the article. Such research, to me, reads as more of a monument to researchers’ ability to be shallow mechanical dolls rather than as an indication that they have *something interesting or compelling to say*. I see this all the time in research that I read: a desperate grasping at theoretical straws in order to impart some profundity to the work, and regardless of whether research is located within any of the numerous subfields/specialties under the mathematics education umbrella or with political-psychoanalytic work which is my own specialty. For example, I have seen plenty of “Freudian” or “Lacanian” papers in our literature that do exactly what Lacan admonishes with his term *poubellication*. I have certainly done this in the past, mostly when I was learning to read philosophy and psychoanalysis, which is a determinate skill. I am certainly not absolved of responsibility for committing the same Lacanian crime myself, but Lacan’s aphorism is always at the front of my mind when writing and it has certainly been a major influence in our editorial work from the very beginning of this Journal’s conception. This is quite simply our way of manifesting our primary motivation for starting this Journal: that research tends to employ “empty speech” whereas we see this as a significant issue and instead want to promote “full speech” which can be conceived of as honest speech, speech spoken without any consideration of the Other’s judgment. We most clearly promote this through our Open Review process, which, notwithstanding the significant differences between speech and writing, does allow “the spoken” to become an integral blueprint for “the written” of the final produced work.

Eat(ing) Shit

When was the last time you ate shit and found it bad? “That shit is bad is a pre-judgment: give it a taste and *then* let us know” (Mieli, 2018, p. 237, emphasis added). This is the example Mieli comes up with to show us how our “adult/mature knowledge” stops us from actually investigating things and coming to know them ourselves. Educational research seems to follow the same structure: research questions, methodologies, theoretical and conceptual frameworks, and analysis strategies are all pre-judged based on what the field has deemed useful or relevant. And of course, the ubiquitous “takeaways and recommendations” sections are always full of prescription drugs to cure symptoms. Lacan admonishes such approaches to knowledge production:

You are all aware of the play on words I have allowed myself around *poubellication* [a combination of *poubelle* (garbage can or rubbish bin) and *publication*; henceforth: ‘rubblication’ or ‘poo-blication’]. A certain number of us have thus been dumped into the same trash can thanks to he³ whose job it was to do so. I could have found myself in worse

³ A criticism of anyone who tries to say “this is what psychoanalysis means/says....” Specifically, Lacan is referring to psychologists such as Piaget who were, at the time, working to incorporate psychoanalysis into a broader philosophical moment of the time which Piaget and many others were calling “structuralism.” While Lacan’s work is arguably structuralist, and I think that it is, this characterization really only serves to orient psychoanalysis in a

company. Indeed, I can hardly be uncomfortable about those with whom I find myself lumped, they being people for whose work I have the highest regard.” (Lacan, 2024, p. 3)

Lacan later recounts this tirade, adding to it the term *publitrashing*. The appearance of three little letters is enough to bring forth its meaning.

It is far from the case that I am criticizing anyone specific. It takes a particular mindset to be a mathematics educator, but it is humorous to me that in the midst of this mindset,

[i]t remains to be recorded that the mathematician has the same embarrassment with his language as we have with the unconscious, and expresses it by this thought that he does not know what he is speaking about, even to assure it as being true. (Lacan, 2009, p. 40)

It takes a particular mindset to be able to produce research on mathematics education, because of mathematics’ singularly signified social role that occurs simultaneously with mathematics education’s polysemy (Cabral & Baldino, 2022), and because of the circularity with which the subject *writes*.

It seems that researchers do not do anything different from schoolchildren or university students, those objects of our fetish which we obsess over. I say fetish-objects here because of the sexual structure of the educational project; Mieli (2018) coined the term *educastration* to describe it:

Society operates repressively on children, above all through an *educastration* designed to eradicate those congenital sexual tendencies deemed ‘perverse.’ ... The objective of *educastration* is the transformation of the infant, in tendency polymorphous and ‘perverse,’ into a heterosexual adult, erotically mutilated but conforming to the Norm. (Mieli, 2018, p. 4, emphasis in original)

Let’s replace some words, and we have “becoming a successful researcher, fantastically⁴ mutilated but conforming to the Norm.”

Coprophilia “Two Ways”

According to Mieli, with whom I also agree, we have a *monstrous shit fetish* but it is perhaps less clear whether it is that we are loving or hating shit. Of course, the fetish means both are true. We obsess over the shit in our classrooms, our shit from our own educational experiences, the shit we perceive as being the barrier to students’ learning and teachers’ teaching, the shit that our students can’t learn mathematics from. There is no “practice standard” for pre-service teachers to have *dealt with their own shit* before being granted a teaching license, and professors certainly don’t have to do this before being allowed to conduct research or train future teachers (see Pais et al., 2017). The old psychoanalytic tenet says that the more that one talks about something, the more they mean the opposite in what they are saying; this is the typical formulation of disavowal (Zupančič, 2024). But it is also the case that the more one talks about something, the more they are angry at someone else due to the other’s words; this is the typical formulation of the sliding of the signifier under the

network of epistemologies; and because psychoanalysis opposes knowledge in the strictest of senses, Lacan rightly is laughing and poking fun at his contemporaries’ writings. Psychoanalysis is also quite poststructuralist, because one of its foundational ideas is the way that meaning is always-already only referential. For Lacan, “[s]tructure should be taken in the sense in which it is most real, in which it is reality itself” (Lacan, 2024, p. 20). Psychoanalysis itself is one of Capital’s innumerable symptoms; qua ideological precipitate, it is singular in that it is trying to “go backwards,” to find the reasons for these symptoms including its own existence. This means that psychoanalysis is structuralist insofar as it is concerned with the gap between reality and non-reality, thus illustrating the impetus of Lacan’s aphorism.

⁴ And hence, also *erotically*.

signified. Lacan says: “That one might be saying remains forgotten behind what is said in what is heard” (Lacan, 2009, p. 32).⁵

Our Open Review process tries to engage this; for my part, I have seen the Open Review as following the structure of a psychoanalysis, occurring over several meetings and over time as a dialogue. Hopefully our Open Reviewers do not mind being, in effect, signed up to be therapists; maybe they get some therapeutic effects from it as well. And of course, the big idealist lie here is that this aspirational effect cannot be guaranteed, nor could its effect even be ascertained. I just have to keep hoping that it happens.

Procreation and Mathematics

Psychology has a long and prominent history in our field; it was one of the first “outside” perspectives to be realized as relevant. However, psychology has a “knowledge problem”: “The trouble is that the psychologist, since he can only support his sector by theology, wants the psychical to be normal, and as a result he elaborates what would repress it” (Lacan, 2009, p. 48).

Lacanian annotator Christian Fierens continues:

The psychologist is caught up in the torment of heteroclitite and changing things while his truth remains unchangeable theology. It is the ‘unhappiness’ of the psychologist, Hegel’s ‘unhappy consciousness.’ Since he is sustained by an eternal and unchangeable God, ‘he wants the psychical’ to be normal.... The psychologist who wants the psychical to be normal falls back then on the zoological schema of an inner world, called on to adapt itself to the cosmological or surrounding world. (Fierens, n.d., p. 73)

The examples are endless: even as I was writing this editorial one day, an opinion article in *The New York Times* appeared in my phone’s notifications that demonstrates the same ideology, one which is so commonplace today that it’s becoming hard to detect its instances. The title of the article was, “There’s a link between therapy culture and childlessness” (Leibowitz, 2025). The author’s basic thrust is that the era of mental health (e.g., counseling, medications, the re-definitions of terms like trauma and abuse) is a primary cause of millennials’ low parenthood rates; her thinking traces a line from going to a therapist, and learning about trauma, to learning about your parents’ role in your childhood experiences, to blaming your parents, to believing that good parenting is at a bar far too impossibly high for you to ever reach, to deciding never to have kids of your own. In other words, the author argues that the epoch of “mental health wokeness” is the reason that my generation (I’m a millennial) doesn’t want to have children.

I will spare the author plenty of due criticism here, but it remains the point that her argument is the typical Western, positivist-psychological, empiricist, capitalist ideology about sexuality—albeit with a new flavor of a chain of seductively sublime logic:

This cultural shift has contributed to a new, nearly impossible standard for parenting. Not only must parents provide shelter, food, safety, and love, but we, their children, also expect them to get us started on successful careers and even to hold themselves accountable for our mental health and happiness well into our adult years. So I want to suggest that there’s another reason my generation dreads parenthood: We’ve held our own parents to

⁵ Alternative translation: “That one might be saying remains forgotten behind the said in what is *understood*.” This alternative signifier—‘understood’ in the place of ‘heard’—I think helps make the point clearer to Western readers because ‘heard’ renders passively whereas ‘understood’ renders actively, which brings forth the import Lacan intends.

unreachable standards, standards that deep down, maybe, we know we ourselves would struggle to meet. (Leibowitz, 2025, paras. 5–6)

While there is certainly some truth to this (Oedipus is the original demonstrator), it falls hilariously short of offering any insights whatsoever—and this is because it is strictly party-line ideology. Mieli again comes to our rescue in understanding this: he calls it the *dogma of procreation*. The dogma of procreation says “love = procreation.” But, as Lacan famously said: *love is giving what you don't have*. For Mieli, “exclusive heterosexuality” is the result of eduction’s ambivalence towards childhood’s “research”—research that Freud showed to be sexual in nature. So, we have a big problem: “education” mutilates us via sexual conformity, and then we expect all of these problems related to students learning to be cured by “the results of mathematics education research?” As Baldino (2024, this volume) explains, “we must not forget that our freshman students are just entering the domain of sexual desire. For them, this page has not yet been turned, hence the proverbial difficulties with calculus” (p. 7). In short, our inner life, regardless of whether or not we have the desire to learn or teach mathematics, sexuality’s eduction has always-already determined what will actually occur in terms of “education.” Families are chosen families, which may or may not include biological relatives. This is easy to understand: the repressed content of “the two become one flesh” (i.e., in the marriage fantasy) is enough to show this common misunderstanding.

Mieli (2018) says that Eros is transsexuality (meaning transsexual in the strict sense, i.e., *transversing all sexualities*), and thus, Eros needs to be liberated. This sexual consequence has direct implications for teaching, as Eros is the driver of wisdom and desire in the liberatory teacher (Garrison, 2010). Eros is thus capacious; and this capaciousness brings with it, from the very first instance, the capaciousness of desire that only glorious, beautiful *turds* can signify.

The liberatory role of eros (and its transsexuality) appears in both the educator’s labor and the athlete’s labor, for example, in the disavowed homoeroticism of sport:

The homosexual idea of sport is very different from the traditional one. The gay schoolboy who detests physical education dreams of a world in which physical exercise, sexual satisfaction, and affection are no longer separate and opposing spheres. ... Instead of punching and beating, play should rather consist in people offering themselves physically to one another, with the erotic character of sadomasochism being openly recognized and combined with affection.” (Mieli, 2018, p. 112)

Both mathematics and sport are masculine-signified; this connection in educational research has been documented (see Moore, 2023), so the connection is obvious: I have previously argued that the enjoyment structure of mathematics education is strictly sadomasochistic (Moore, 2024). As with Mieli’s flating of supposed “homophobia” in sport, I also say that without avowing this erotic pain and pleasure of mathematics, teachers and researchers are acting as the “phobic” agents of control rather than liberation.

The more something is repressed, the more it is expressed through language—in what is said, and what is not said. It comes out of us, and we enjoy getting it out.

A Voluminous Shit, I Mean, Volume

The authors in this volume of the Journal know the enjoyment of retaining and releasing at the appropriate time. This volume is our first double-issue; this decision was due to the volume of excellent submissions we received for it. Some needed redirecting, and others did not, but all are quite timely nowadays in 2025. It is clear worldwide that this is a significant year from a scientific

perspective of history. Ole Skovsmose and Julian Williams died, both magnates of our field. Extreme political tensions and genocides are occurring. Entire cultures are at risk of being extinguished in Capital's name. So, this is the time to "release."

Ernest (2024, 2025) treats the reader to two book reviews in this volume; they are about Ole Skovsmose's latest and final works, *Critical Mathematics Education* and *Critical Philosophy of Mathematics*. The Journal's parent organization held book launches for both. Skovsmose's recent death was a shitty thing to happen. These are both foundational texts; I encourage you to add both of them to your reading lists.

From Killi and Xenofontos (2024) comes an article on immigrant students in the Norwegian context. Immigrants worldwide are facing persecution currently. They appear in all of our classrooms. Rather than being scared of what our governments might do, the authors reminds us excluding these sojourners is strictly incompatible with Teaching. We should take their lead and double-down on supporting immigrants; their mathematics classes are a small but pivotal factor in their lives. Supporting immigrants is one of the hallmarks of good teaching, and it is frankly the least anyone who calls themselves a serious Teacher can do.

Rios and colleagues (2024) give us another treat with the same import: the use of poetry-as-method to inquire into multilingual students' experiences in undergraduate mathematics. The article, the methodology of which is compelling, goes a long way in reminding us of the realities of our actual students in university courses; the article's argument is timely, to say the least.

Pastora and colleagues (2024) bring a radical critique of proofs courses in undergraduate mathematics. Written by a professor and two of their about their proofs course together, this article is an exemplar of what we aim to promote with this Journal: a space to communicate how radically re-thinking of our work can have significant impacts on what our field's discourse.

Thanheiser and colleagues (2024) add another article in the same vein: they present an article that was borne out of their panel discussion at the Association of Mathematics Teacher Educators' conference last year about the AMTE Standards. Standards are normative; hence, there is always a contradiction between standardization and liberation. These authors, from various perspectives, talk about how they are trying to make sense of the AMTE Standards from tarrying with the contradiction. The result is a prescient and timely insight for any mathematics teacher educator.

Baldino (2024) pushes our thinking to the brink of ecstasy. In this article, he shows the psychoanalytic origins of students' mathematical difficulties, tying them rightly to sexuality, language, and enjoyment. The article served as the initial inspiration to theme this editorial around shit. As I write this in 2025, Baldino's health is deteriorating. What he has given us here in this article is a profound gift. Read it. It is some of his clearest work ever.

Also quite clear is the work of Anonymous (2024), who gives us an admonition of the Palestinian genocide that is currently happening. I encourage you to read the afterword as well: this was the first paper we had been asked to publish anonymously. I am thankful to the other editors for their work in discerning how to approach this request given the context and political situation. The afterword captures all of our thinking. Perhaps someday we can tell you who wrote it.

Cannon and colleagues (2025) give us a unique analysis of the connection between teachers' views of mathematics and the significant social marker of mathematical failure. They conduct this work with elementary teachers. Although they do not say it, their study avows the role of language positioning us in the world and shows how this shapes our actions and how our emotions are licensed and censored by ideology.

Next come two articles on neurodiversity, one of is our first publication on physics education. McDermott (2025) gives an exciting new perspective on neurodiversity and queer theory in physics

education. In particular, the article ties neuroqueerness to physics literacy and shows how the scientific ideology can usurp its own potential for inquiry. We follow this with Norton's (2025) emotion-wrenching autoethnography on undiagnosed neurodivergence and its consequences for teachers and students of mathematics.

This voluminous volume concludes with two artistic journeys. In the first, Ávila Betancourt and colleagues (2025) give a striking incision into art, history, and mathematics education; this is an important article because it gives a pedagogical account of this connection with explicit elaborations in the classroom setting. Secondly, Fan (2025) brings an exciting inquiry into emotions and emotional labor, and mathematics education. The article brings up many good insights about the impossibility of separating educational content from the psyche.

The Bidet: A Radical Gift

What I and the other *Journal* staff have attempted to do over the past four years is to show the hilarious self-defeat of categories in mathematics education research, chiefly among which is the category of “this is mathematics education research” and “this isn't mathematics education research.” In Tim Dean's words, what we have tried to do is to “loosening [‘progressive/sociocultural’ mathematics education research] into *something more capacious*” (Dean, 2018, p. xi, emphasis added). What I *hope* is the most obvious evidence of this is in how we have published research that challenges normative approaches to *even* the progressivist/sociocultural research. Since knowledge is sexual, I draw a homology between the development of sexual identity discourse and mathematics education *qua* field. Fifty years ago, mathematics education was beginning as a field; at the same time, the Gay movement, being bound up with the civil rights advances of the 1960s and 1970s, was also pigeon-holing itself into categorical identity politics. Whilst this is certainly necessary for political reasons in capitalism, it ultimately does nothing for the liberation. I don't have to brainstorm very hard to see the connection here: we had several decades of the psychological movement, then socioculturalism (still via mostly Western epistemology) started to become the main thread of our field. While I appreciate such scholars' interventions, I find it difficult to lie to myself and say that “things are better.” Of course, we have some important new pedagogical insights. Students do learn mathematics better when they are the ones doing most of the signifying themselves; we have active learning and all its derivatives to thank for this. Students do not learn mathematics in a vacuum, rather, they learn it in a social context where it is signified bourgeois-ly, White-ly, and heteronormatively, and thus students learn mathematics better when we understand the social relations and identities that marginalize students; we have countless minority scholars to thank for this.

The subtext remains however that these interventions are aimed at remedying defective “mandatory” learning. My wager, informed by nothing other than basic psychoanalysis, is that every single one of us has taken a career in mathematics education simply because we enjoy it. The important next question is, then: what exactly is it that I/we enjoy? On one level, what I personally enjoy is the “insulation” provided by the fact that it seems as if the “task of” mathematics education will never be done: (most) people will never understand mathematics, it will always be special, privileged knowledge; so, it's difficult for anyone to critique what I do or replace me (with at least some reasonable level of surety) with a machine to do my job for me. This is a dangerous admission for a professor to make; but I wonder how generalizable that claim is.

The truth is that every single one of our students is in our classrooms in order to *pass*. That is their desire, overdetermined as it was for them by Capital itself. The primary symptom of this is that our students are there for non-mathematical reasons, and so, we—the researchers—start talking all of these discourses to conceal the fact that our desires *are not our students'*. Our discourses

help us sublimate this gap. This is a criticism of ideology, not of anyone's conscious intentionalities. This is perhaps best illustrated by the current state of affairs in my own classrooms: students hate the prospect of taking a course in mathematics; they are happy to "just go home and watch some videos online"; they are happy to use AI to "help them learn" (which is a bunch of nonsense; see Barros, 2025). All of this occurs *in the midst of* five decades of our field's extant literature. As Pais said, "[the situation in schools nowadays is] stagnant if not worse" (Pais, 2024, p. 513). I conclude, then, that one of the enjoyments of the mathematics education researcher is in sublimating and disavowing *actes raté*. The original *acte raté* is the baby who shits themselves, having not yet learned the profound enjoyment of *retaining and releasing* the feces when called upon by the Big Other, viz. when it is appropriate to defecate (Baldino, 2024).

"[T]he fault, as usual, belongs to the specialists" (Lacan, 1989, p. 55). We are the specialists; we are Capital's educational specialists. We have been trained and work inside the neoliberal university and society. The ideology that we have no choice but to obey "rejects and condemns manifest anal eroticism, or else it effectively ghettoizes it, since the rule of capital is based, among other things, on the repression of anality and its sublimation" (Mieli, 2018, p. 156). This is hardly a new claim. But what about the bidet: the appliance that can signify a different mindset, one that returns to the childhood polymorphous curiosity, allowing our sexuality to be *transsexual* and thus *Erotic*. These were the states of our psyches when we were in school, when we were forming enduring affinities and fears about all things our teachers were in charge of telling us about, in the midst of their own mutilated psyches. My goal with this editorial was to be "a bidet" to impress upon you the openness, the daydream, the liberation, and the revolutionary worldview that is possible. But we must first deal with our own shit by "cleaning it out," hence the radicality of the bidet. In a moment where I have not found a teacher who says they are *not exhausted by the educational labor*, I once again enlist the help of Mieli for some clarity:

It is the function of ideology to obscure the authentic 'nature' of capital, to negate the human, corporeal foundations that sustain it: the whole shoddy mess is held up by our alienated labour, our repressed libido, our estranged energy. Taking full account of this leads to the acquisition of a revolutionary consciousness and a revolutionary libido. As Luciano Parinetto writes: 'the proletarian revolution too must pass through the asshole.' (Mieli, 2018, pp. 156–157)

And this is what I would like to leave you with, as a dear reader of this Journal.

If what in homosexuality especially horrifies *homo normalis*, that cop of the hetero-capitalist system, is getting fucked in the ass, then this can only mean that one of the most delicious bodily pleasures, anal sex, bears in itself a remarkable revolutionary force. The thing for which we queens are so greatly condemned contains a large part of our subversive gay potentiality. I hoard my treasure in my ass, but my ass is open to everyone... (Mieli, 2018, p. 157)

We are all guilty of being the policeman of mathematics education: it is, in part, why we are here doing these careers in our field. We enjoy being the policeman; it absolves us of some guilt about capitalism's hegemony. But this is the same kernel where our revolutionary potential is also held—and it turns out, as I hope to have shown in this editorial, to be located in the ass. What kind of delicious pleasure could you get from opening yourself up *in and through* your research, through the *it's written* that counsels you through the process of doing the academic labor?

Flowers and turds are both beautiful, dialectics teaches us. We are taught to have relationships with them both, but *not too intimately, not too much research on them*. The turds are gross and smell bad; the flowers have pollen which will give you an allergic outbreak. Appreciate the turds at a distance,

the Big Other tells us, but don't tarry with them too long, that would be unacceptable. I continue to be skeptical of anyone who tells me "this is what you should think and do and say." The fact that we have ideological incursions that dictate such things to us is enough evidence to make my point, but the levity of this connection never ceases to surprise me as to its extensive reach in our work as scholars.

As I step down from four years at the helm, I think back on all the articles I have had a part in publishing. I think back on all the work all of us have done to build this Journal from scratch. I think back on all the work done by the authors and reviewers, which is immense. I think back on all the warm chuckles of affection that escaped from my mouth when I saw other publication outlets doing things differently that seemed anything other than coincidental. I think back on all the emails received and conversations had, the ones where I heard about how this Journal was being taken up in the field, whether that be from unknown colleagues from far away telling me they are teaching our papers, or to hear that editors at more prestigious journals were considering us an important source of literature. These are the kinds of memories that make my exit from *JTM-ME* more edifying and less sad. In my view, this project has proven successful, and I will wait eagerly to see what the editorial leadership do next. I only have one lingering question to ask: "Hey, kid⁶—do you want to come play in the turds with us?" It is my hope that the *Journal* encourages us all to make our asses more capacious; they are, after all, where we hoard all our treasure.

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⁶ An appeal to the reader's inner, polymorphous, 'perverse', capacious child. I am indebted to colleague Dr. Julian Fleron for bestowing on me the gift of this beautiful, simple question's magnanimity: "Hey kid, want to come play?"

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